

Figures S1 to S20. Diagrammatic representation of typical sequences of reproductive calls plotted at two time scales. First, they are plotted over a 40 second duration and presented as waveforms (oscillograms). Where the call recorded was shorter than 40 seconds the call is copied and repeated to demonstrate the calling sequence, and where a call sequence exceeded 40 seconds that is noted in the caption, since these are necessarily clipped in the figures. Second, they are plotted over a 2, 4 or 6 second duration, whichever is most appropriate to present one or two call, and they are presented as waveforms and spectrograms. In some cases, calls were filtered to remove extraneous background sounds so that call structure is clear. Numerous of the calls are taken from publicly available sources such a digital field guides and published media (tapes, CD recordings, websites, and applications) [Hoskins, et al. (2017), Littlejohn (1987), Queensland Museum (1990), Queensland Museum (1990), Roberts (2006), Stewart (1998, 2002)] and for those illustrated the name of the recordist and location where available is included.

Figures S1 & S1-1. *Amnihyla*, *Exochohyla*, *Hyalotos*, *Ischnohyla*. Calls of defined duration, simple and complex, note repetition with distinctive note and pulse structure, amplitude modulated, DF moderate. *Amnihyla*, Simple calls, one species with note repetition, fully amplitude modulated notes, other with single note with observable pulses, DF moderate. **A)** *A. angiana*, upper Kikori River basin, NG, SJR, **B)** *A. arfarkiana*, Western Province NG, SJR. *Exochohyla*. Complex calls, defined duration, notes fully amplitude modulated some with are note repetition and others with dense pulses, DF moderate to high. **C)** *E. chrisdahli*, Wamangu NG, C. Dahl, **D)** *E. humboldtorum*, Foyas NG, SJR. *Hyalotos*. Complex call, defined duration, notes fully amplitude modulated, note repetition, DF high. **E)** *H. richardsi*, Darai Plateau, SJR. *Ischnohyla*. Simple and complex calls, defined duration, notes with moderate pulse repetition, notes are not fully amplitude modulated in all species, DF high. **F)** *I. daraiensis*, Darai Plateau, NG, SJR, **G)** *I. gracilis* upper Strickland River basin, NG, SJR, **H)** *I. nigropunctata*, Mamb NG, SJR.

Figure S2 & S2-1. *Carichyla*. Complex calls of short notes that are fully amplitude modulated, defined duration, DF high. **A)** *C. bicolor*, Mount Molloy Qld., D. Stewart.

A

Figures S3 & S3-1. *Chlorohyla*. Calls of defined duration, simple and complex, note repetition with distinctive note and pulse structure, amplitude modulated, DF modulation. **A)** *C. auae*, Herowana NG, SJR, **B)** *C. bella*, north Qld, C Hoskin, **C)** *C. chloris*, Nightcap Range NSW, MJM, **D)** *C. gracilenta*, Nightcap Range NSW, MJM, **E)** *C. xanthomera* Atherton Tablelands Qld, SJR.

Figures S4 & S4-1. Monotypic genera. *Coggerdonia*, *Eremnoculus*, *Melvillihyla*, *Saganura*, *Sylvagemma* and *Teretistes*. **A)** *Coggerdonia adelaidensis*, call with defined duration, complex, multi-notes, amplitude modulated, DF high, southwest WA, JD Roberts, **B)** *Eremnoculus dayi* Wet Tropic, Qld, D. Stewart, **C)** *Melvillihyla andiirrmalin*, call is a single short tonal note, defined duration, emitted in long train, DF moderate. M. Cape Melville, Qld, C. Hoskin, **D)** *Saganura burrowsae*, call one note with moderately dense pulses of defined duration, repeated in long call trains, moderate DF. southwestern Tas, D. Milledge, **E)** *Sylvagemma brevipalmata*. call of non-defined duration consists of rapidly emitted single tonal notes in long trains, with inter-note interval decreasing or increasing irregularly, DF moderate. Cooperook NSW, MJM, **F)** *Teretistes havina*, complex call, defined duration, fully amplitude modulated tonal notes, note repetition and note with dense pulses, high DF. Moran NG, SJR.

Figure S5 & S5-1. *Colleeneremia*. Calls of defined duration, simple, multi-note calls with dense pulse structure, some with frequency modulation, DF high. **A)** *C. balatus*, Bunya Mountains Qld, H. Hines, **B)** *C. dentata*, Dorrigo Plateau, NSW, MJM, **C)** *C. electrica*, Croydon Qld, S. McDonald, **D)** *C. pygmaea*, Wamangu PNG, C Dahl, **E)** *C. quiritatus*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM, **F)** *C. rubella*, Eungella Range, Qld, MJM.

Figures S6 & S6-1. *Cyclorana*. Call simple, single note of defined duration produced in long trains, notes tonal, amplitude modulated with dense pulses, DF low to moderate. **A)** *C. alboguttata*, St Lawrence Qld., D. Stewart, **B)** *C. australis*, Kununurra WA, D. Stewart, **C)** *C. brevipes*, Calliope Qld., D. Stewart, **D)** *C. cultripes*, Yelarbon Qld., D. Stewart, **E)** *C. cryptotis*, Wakooka Station, Qld., K. McDonald, P. Doughty, **F)** *C. longipes*, P. Doughty, Kimberly, WA, **G)** *C. maculosa*, D. Stewart, Daly Waters NT, **H)** *C. maini*, Uluru NT, MJM, **I)** *C. manya*, Qld., D. Stewart, **J)** *C. novaehollandiae*, Mitchell, Qld., D. Stewart, **K)** *C. occidentalis*, Yalgoo WA, MJM, **L)** *C. platycephala*, Yelarbon, Qld., D. Stewart, **M)** *C. vagitus*, Kimberly WA, P. Doughty, **N)** *C. verrucosa*, Yelarbon Qld., D. Stewart.

Figure S7 & S7-1. *Drymomantis*. Complex calls of short notes that are fully amplitude modulated, defined duration, DF high. **A)** *D. bicolor*, Mount Molloy Qld., D. Stewart, **B)** *D. cooloolensis*, Cooloola Qld., D. Stewart, **C)** *D. fallax*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM, **D)** *D. olongburensis* Tyagarah, Northeast NSW, MJM.

Figures S8, 8(1) & S8-1. *Dryopsophus*. Simple and complex calls some with note repetition, defined duration, some with frequency modulation, DF moderate to high. **A)** *D. barringtonensis*, Barrington Range NSW, MJM, **B)** *D. daviesae*, Hastings Range NSW, MJM, **C)** *D. kroombitensis*, Kroombit Tops Qld., D. Stewart, **D)** *D. nudidigita*, Southeast NSW, D. Stewart. **E)** *D. pearsoniana*, Border Ranges Qld., D. Stewart, **F)** *D. phyllochroa*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM, **G)** *D. spenceri*, Kinglake Vic., M. Littlejohn, **H)** *D. subglandulosa*, Gibraltar Range NSW, MJM.

A**Time (s)**

Figures S9 & S9-1. *Kallistobatrachus*, *Leptobatrachus*, *Megatestes*, *Nasutibatrachus*. **A to E)** *Kallistobatrachus*, Simple and complex calls, defined duration, some with short tonal pulses, others note repetition and others moderately pulsatile, moderate to high DF, **A)** *K. beryllinus*, upper Sepik River basin, NG, SJR, **B)** *K. iris*, Porgera NG, SJR, **C)** *K. lisae*, Agogo Range, NG, SJR, **D)** *K. majikthise*, Tabubil, NG, SJR, **E)** *K. richardsi*, Darai NG, SJR. **F and G)** *Leptobatrachus*, simple call, defined duration, single note densely pulsatile, DF moderate, **F)** *L. thesaurensis*, Vouvou NG SJR. **G)** *L. insularis* Nakani Moutains, East New Britain Province, NG, SJR, **H)** *Megatestes dahlii*, simple call defined duration note repetition, notes densely pulsatile, DF low, C. Hudson, Fogg Dam NT, **I and J)** *Nasutibatrachus*, simple calls, defined duration, several short notes fully amplitude modulated in rapid sequence, DF moderate, **I)** *N. mucro*, Wamangu NG, SJR, **J)** *N. pronimia*, Moran NG, SJR.

Figures S10 & S10-1. *Litoria*. Calls are simple and mostly of non-defined duration, notes are fully amplitude modulated and emitted in long trains, often with inter-note interval being altered, some with frequency modulation, moderate DF. **A)** *L. axillaris*, Prince Regent River, Kimberly region, WA, P. Doughty, **B)** *L. coplandi*, King Leopold Range WA, MJM, **C)** *L. freycineti*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM, **D)** *L. inermis*, Atherton Tablelands Qld, MJM, **E)** *L. latopalmata*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM, **F)** *L. nasuta*, Kew NSW, MJM, **G)** *L. nigrofrenata*, Mount Molloy Qld, D. Stewart, **H)** *L. pallida*, Darwin NT, D. Stewart, **I)** *L. personata*, Kakadu NT, A. Stewart, **J)** *L. spaldingi*, NT. D. Trembath, **K)** *L. tornieri*, western Arnhemland, NT, A. Stewart, **L)** *L. watjulumensis* western Arnhemland, NT, A. Stewart.

Figures S11 & S11-1. *Mahonabatrachus*. Simple and complex calls, short tonal notes that can be emitted in long sequences and non-defined duration, DF high. **A)** *M. aurifera*, northwest Kimberley WA, **B)** *M. longirostris*, Cape Melville, Qld, K. McDonald, **C)** *M. meiriana*, western Arnhemland, NT, A. Stewart, **D)** *M. microbelos*, Gordonvale Qld, D. Stewart, **E)** *M. timida*, Tabubil, NG, SJR.

Time (s)

0.5 1 1.5

Time (s)

Figures S12 & S12-1. *Mosleyia*. Simple calls, short tonal notes, defined duration, DF moderate, frequency modulation is some species. **A)** *M. dayi*, Mosman Gorge Qld, D. Stewart, **B)** *M. nannotis*, Mount Lewis Qld, D. Stewart, **C)** *M. nyakalensis*, Windsor Tablelands Qld, D. Stewart, **D)** *M. rheocola*. Kuranda, Qld, D. Stewart.

A

Time (s)

Time (s)

Figure S13 & S13-1. *Papuahyla*. Complex calls of short notes that are fully amplitude modulated, defined duration, DF high. **A)** *P. chloristona*, Purari River basin, NG, SJR, **B)** *P. lodesdema*, East New Britain, NG, SJR.

Figures S14 & S14-1. *Pelodryas*. Simple call, note repetition, notes densely pulsatile, defined duration, often emitted in long call trains, DF low. **A)** *P. caerulea* Wamangu NG, C. Dahl, **B)** *P. cavernicola*, Kimberleys, WA, P Doughty, **C)** *P. gilleni*, Central Ranges NT, A. Stewart, **D)** *P. splendida*, Kimberleys WA, A. Stewart.

A

Figures S15 & S15-1. *Pengilleyia*. Simple call, note repetition, amplitude modulated notes, defined duration, DF moderate. **A)** *P. amboinensis*, Gobe, NG, SJR, **B)** *P. darlingtoni*, upper Kikori River basin, NG, SJR, **C)** *P. peroni*, Central Coast Range NSW, NJM, **D)** *P. rothii*, Darwin, NT, D. Stewart, **E)** *P. tyleri*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM.

Time (s)

Figures S16 & S16-1. *Ranoidea*. Complex calls with dense pulsatile notes not fully amplitude modulated, defined duration, DF low. **A)** *R. aurea*, Koorangang Island NSW, MJM, **B)** *R. castanea*, Southern Tablelands ACT, D Hunter, **C)** *R. cyclorhynchus*, southwest WA, JD Robert, **D)** *R. moorei*, Perth WA, JD Roberts, **E)** *R. raniformis*, Nampoo SA, J. Voros.

Figures S17 & S17-1. *Rawlinsonia*. Simple call, note repetition, amplitude modulated notes, defined duration, DF moderate. **A)** *R. corbeni*, Atherton Tablelands Qld, L Price, **B)** *R. ewingii*, Moyston Vic, L. Price, **C)** *R. jervisiensis*, Myall Lakes NSW, MJM, **D)** *R. littlejohni*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM, **E)** *R. paraewingi*, Vic, M. Littlejohn, **F)** *R. revelata*, Cooperook NSW, MJM, **G)** *R. verreauxii*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM, **H)** *R watsoni*, Parma Creek Nature Reserve NSW, MJM.

Figures S18 & S18-1. *Rhyaconastes*. Calls of defined duration, note repetition but poorly amplitude modulated, notes densely pulsatile. **A)** *R. booroolongensis*, Moombi Range NSW, D. Stewart, **B)** *R. jungguy*, Atherton Tablelands Qld., C. Hoskin, **C)** *R. lesueuri*, Merrica River, NSW MJM, **D)** *R. wilcoxii*, Central Coast Range NSW, MJM.

A

Figures S19 & S19-1. *Sandyrana*. Calls consist of short tonal notes, defined duration, often repeated in long call trains, DF low. **A)** *S. infrafnata*, Cairns Qld, MJM, **B)** *S. multicolor*, Wondiwoi Mtns, NG, R. Günther, **C)** *S. purpureolata*, Mamberamo River basin, NG, SJR, **D)** *S. sanguinolenta*, Snow Mtns, NG, SJR, **E)** *S. sauroni*, Darai NG, SJR.

Time (s)

0 0.5 1 1.5 2

Time (s)

Figures S20 & S20-1. *Spicicalyx*. Simple calls of defined duration, series of short tonal notes fully amplitude modulated, note repetition, DF moderate. **A)** *S. eucnemis* McIlwraith Range, Qld., D. Stewart, **B)** *S. genimaculata*, Waigeo NG, SJR, **C)** *S. myola*, Atherton Tablelands Qld., C Hoskin, **D)** *S. serrata* Lamb Range Qld., C Hoskin.

